

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SHAH****FIRST NAME: DIPEN****PROGRAM CODE: LLM****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Pr. Laurent CLEENEWERCK**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

ELEMENTS OF WRITING PROCESS

1) INTRODUCTION

Studying for academics or learning, requires for its in-depth understanding, a thorough grasp of its principles and tools, to place it in real-world practice. And to this end, Euclid's method of writing response papers for every period of study undertaken is apposite since we cannot write without a thorough reading and understanding of principles, concepts, and illustrations. Writing of essay, which aims at responding to provided course material with appropriate references, creates a learning system which is insightful and methodical and encourages analysis.

This response paper will discuss the importance of reading, researching, analyzing, and drawing your logical conclusions before writing. Further, I will discuss the relevance of the structure and principles of coherence and cohesion in writing essays for academic papers. To accomplish the task, I shall begin by drawing the outline of the essay and defining the question to be answered, and then I shall carry out the extensive reading of the subject to find out issues and problems to be presented, answered or contradicted. Having thus explored the ideas and principles as well as its application I shall take notes of various ideas in support of (or to contradict) the problem which I am answering, and then I shall discuss how data should be organized and structured before starting to write. In the end, I shall discuss the structure of the essay and the use of various elements like plagiarism and logical flow using coherence and cohesion.

2) READING AND RESEARCHING TO ANALYSE

Writing on a topic is not a reproduction of knowledge in ordinary parlance, but evidence-based analysis of facts and information carefully gathered by various researchers or scientists in the field. It is stated that only good reading produces a good writing style but most important is that a writer must think before he writes, and reading of materials on the topic that others have written provides a context and stimulates analysis thus contributing to meaning and idea (Anmarie, 12–14). Hence thought synthesis is undertaken to organize ideas, to answer the main topic of an essay by analysing data, which in turn would ultimately define the outline of the structure and logical flow of essay before the actual writing takes place (EUCLID 2015,1-3).

3) WRITING ESSAY

Every essay has a structure in which information is presented in a manner so that, the reader is easily able to grasp the central meaning and argument on the thesis statement. An essay thus is comprised of an introductory paragraph containing a summary of the topic, followed by the argument and followed by a sequence of evidenced-based ideas supporting the point. That each evidence-based idea than becomes the body of the essay, which gets divided into as many paragraphs as the points discussed in support of the argument. Finally, the conclusion will comprise, summaries of main points and writers reflect on the same. Thus entire framework from writing the introduction to conclusion forms the written essay on a topic which we discussed, argued, and supported by evidence (Euclid 2015, 4–5).

a) Quotation to Prevent Plagiarism

Plagiarism is using somebody's work but not giving him credit by mentioning his name. It is a serious offense in law and an unethical practice. To illustrate the same if you are writing a response paper on the art of writing, and if you quote a passage from Alber Camus work without mentioning the source, it would be unethical practice, attracting penalty by law. Hence reproducing others' work and not giving their due by referring must be avoided (Euclid 2015, 6–8).

However, to avoid plagiarism, cite the source by quoting (Euclid 2015, 9–12). There are various methods to cite like an in-text quotation, list of works cited, paraphrase, and signal phrases. There are various formats available to cite. Specialized software like Zotero, Mendley, and others are indispensable for citation, on account of their integration with Microsoft Word.

b) Coherence and Cohesion for Logical Flow

I would argue that the most important aspect of writing being coherence and cohesion, is not satisfactorily discussed in Euclid's ACA-401 Period 1 Coursepack. Coherence is a method of providing information so that it has a logical connection with the topic under discussion and internally within paragraphs. Sentences within paragraphs provide unity with other sentences in the body and with the thesis statement. The latter is generally known as cohesion and former as register. Ann M. Johns, in her article, Coherence and Academic Writing in 1986, quotes the following:

Armbruster and Anderson (1984) speaks of discourse which meets reader expectations and provides guidance through the text as "reader considerate".

This review of current literature provides a number of principles to guide instructors in teaching the concept of coherence:

1. Coherence is text based and consists of the ordering and interlinking of propositions within a text by use of appropriate information structure (including cohesion)
2. At the same time, coherence is reader based; the audience and the assignment must be consistently considered as the discourse is produced and revised
3. Instructors have an obligation to teach coherence comprehensively, that is, to take into account these two approaches (text based and reader based), at a minimum. (TESOL 1986, 5).

Therefore, for better understanding of readers, how and when to organize ideas by interlinking of information through sentences, is a structure which is most crucial for essay to be successful in conveying the argument in explanation of topic under discussion.

4) CONCLUSION

Thus, writing essay besides being a planned activity carried out after thorough research of the subject, is also a matter of arranging the flow of ideas by using a structure and sentence connectors for easy understanding of argument by the reader. This art of writing making different paragraphs one whole symphony of an idea which is an art which requires learning beyond these basic principles.

REFERENCES

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